

**ELEMENTARY ESTIMATES FOR THE NUMBER OF PURE
NUMBER FIELDS OF DEGREE p**

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Abstract

Let p be an odd prime number, and X a large real number. In this note, we consider the lower and upper bounds of the number of pure number fields of degree p with the absolute values of discriminants at most X by elementary methods.

1. Introduction

Let n be a positive integer, X a large positive number, and $N_n(X)$ the number of number fields F of degree n with $|d(F)| \leq X$. Here $d(F)$ is the discriminant of a number field F . A well-known conjecture asserts that

$$N_n(X) \sim c_n X$$

for some c_n . This conjecture has been proved for $n = 2, 3, 4$, and 5 ([3], [1], [2]). However, this problem is very difficult and deep. In this paper, we consider the distribution of pure number fields of odd prime degree by elementary methods.

Let p be an odd prime number, and F a number field of degree p . If there exists a p -free positive integer $n > 1$ such that $F = \mathbb{Q}(\sqrt[p]{n})$, then we shall call F a pure number field of degree p . (If there is no prime number l such that $l^k | n$, then n is said to be k -free.) For $X > 0$, we denote the number of pure number fields F of degree p with $|d(F)| \leq X$ by $P_p(X)$.

Theorem 1. *For an odd prime number p , we have*

$$\frac{B_p}{\zeta(2)} X^{\frac{1}{p-1}} \leq P_p(X) \leq \frac{A_p}{\zeta(p)} X$$

where $\zeta(s)$ is the Riemann zeta function,

$$A_p = \frac{p^{p+1} - p^{p-1} + p^{p-2} - 1}{(p^p - 1)p^p},$$

and

$$B_p = \frac{1}{(p+1)p^{\frac{p-2}{p-1}}} + \frac{p}{(p+1)p^{\frac{p}{p-1}}}.$$

For example, $P_3(X)$ is the number of pure cubic fields F with $|d(F)| \leq X$, and

$$\frac{1}{2\sqrt{3}\zeta(2)}\sqrt{X} \leq P_3(X) \leq \frac{37}{351\zeta(3)}X.$$

To show this theorem, we use two important lemmas.

First, we explain a result of Cohen and Robinson [4]. Let $k, q > 1$ be positive integers, $a \in \mathbb{Z}/q\mathbb{Z}$, and X a real positive large number. We set

$$Q_k(X; a, q) = \#\{n : k\text{-free} \leq X, n \equiv a \pmod{q}\}.$$

If there is a k -free positive integer n such that $n \equiv a \pmod{q}$, then $n = cq + a$ for some $c \in \mathbb{Z}$ and $\gcd(a, q)$ must be k -free. Thus, since $Q_k(X; a, q) = 0$ when $\gcd(a, q)$ is not k -free, we assume $\gcd(a, q)$ is k -free.

A divisor $d > 0$ of q is called a unitary divisor when $\gcd(d, q/d) = 1$. If d is a unitary divisor of q , we write $d|_*q$. The largest unitary divisor of q which is a divisor of a is denoted by $(a, q)_*$. Moreover, we denote the core of H by H_0 . Namely, H_0 is the largest square-free divisor of H .

In [4], Cohen and Robinson proved the following result.

Lemma 1. *Let $H := (a, q)_*$. We have*

$$Q_k(X; a, q) = \frac{q^{k-1}}{J_k(q)} \frac{\varphi^*(H_0^k/H)}{H_0^k/H} \frac{1}{\zeta(k)} X + O(\sqrt[k]{X})$$

where

$$J_k(n) = n^k \prod_{\substack{l|n \\ l:\text{prime}}} \left(1 - \frac{1}{l^k}\right)$$

and

$$\varphi^*(n) = n \prod_{\substack{l^e|_*n \\ l:\text{prime}}} \left(1 - \frac{1}{l^e}\right).$$

For example, if $H = 1$, then

$$Q_k(X; a, q) = \frac{1}{q} \prod_{\substack{l|q \\ l:\text{prime}}} \left(1 - \frac{1}{l^k}\right)^{-1} \frac{1}{\zeta(k)} X + O(\sqrt[k]{X}).$$

Next lemma computes the discriminants of pure number fields.

Lemma 2 (Fujisaki [5], p.133). *Let p be an odd prime number, n a p -free positive integer, and n_0 the core of n . Put $F = \mathbb{Q}(\sqrt[p]{n})$. We have*

$$d(F) = \begin{cases} (-1)^{\frac{p-1}{2}} p^{p-2} (n_0)^{p-1} & \text{if } n^{p-1} \equiv 1 \pmod{p^2}, \\ (-1)^{\frac{p-1}{2}} p^p (n_0)^{p-1} & \text{if } n^{p-1} \not\equiv 1 \pmod{p^2}. \end{cases}$$

Since the author doesn't find the proof of this lemma in the literature, and the original proof was published in Japanese, we shall sketch the proof here. Every p -free positive integer n can be put uniquely into the form $n = \prod_{i=1}^{p-1} a_i^i$ where $a_i \in \mathbb{Z}_{>0}$ and $n_0 = \prod_{i=1}^{p-1} a_i$. Put

$$\alpha_j = \left(\prod_{i=1}^{p-1} a_i^{ij - \lfloor \frac{ij}{p} \rfloor p} \right)^{\frac{1}{p}}$$

for $j = 0, 1, \dots, p-1$. Let \mathfrak{n} be the \mathbb{Z} -module generated by $\alpha_0, \dots, \alpha_{p-1}$. We can check $d(\mathfrak{n}) = (O_F : \mathfrak{n})^2 d(F)$ where O_F is the ring of integers of F , and $d(\mathfrak{n})$ is the discriminant of \mathfrak{n} as \mathbb{Z} -module. By algebraic argument, we obtain

$$d(\mathfrak{n}) = (-1)^{\frac{p-1}{2}} p^p (n_0)^{p-1}$$

and

$$(O_F : \mathfrak{n}) = \begin{cases} p & \text{if } n^{p-1} \equiv 1 \pmod{p^2}, \\ 1 & \text{if } n^{p-1} \not\equiv 1 \pmod{p^2}. \end{cases}$$

For more details, refer to [5].

2. Proof

First, we consider the upper bound. It is obvious that

$$\begin{aligned} P_p(X) &\leq \#\{n : p\text{-free} > 1, |d(\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt[p]{n}))| \leq X\} \\ &= \sum_{a=1}^{p^2} \#\{n : p\text{-free} > 1, n \equiv a \pmod{p^2}, |d(\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt[p]{n}))| \leq X\} \\ &=: \sum_{a=1}^{p^2} P_{p,a}(X). \end{aligned}$$

If $a^{p-1} \equiv 1 \pmod{p^2}$, we have

$$P_{p,a}(X) = \#\{n : p\text{-free} > 1, n \equiv a \pmod{p^2}, p^{p-2} n_0^{p-1} \leq X\}$$

by Lemma 2. Since $n \leq n_0^{p-1}$ for p -free number n , we see

$$P_{p,a}(X) \leq Q_p\left(\frac{X}{p^{p-2}}; a, p^2\right)$$

in this case. Similarly, if $a^{p-1} \not\equiv 1 \pmod{p^2}$, we obtain

$$P_{p,a}(X) \leq Q_p\left(\frac{X}{p^p}; a, p^2\right)$$

by Lemma 2.

We can estimate $Q_p(X; a, p^2)$ for $a = 1, 2, \dots, p^2$ by using Lemma 1. Note that $(a, p^2)_* = p^2$ if $a = p^2$ and $(a, p^2)_* = 1$ otherwise. Thus, we have

$$Q_p(X; a, p^2) \sim \frac{p^{p-2}}{p^p - 1} \frac{1}{\zeta(p)} X,$$

when $a = 1, \dots, p^2 - 1$, and

$$Q_p(X; p^2, p^2) \sim \frac{p^{p-2} - 1}{p^p - 1} \frac{1}{\zeta(p)} X.$$

Therefore, for a large number X , we obtain that

$$\begin{aligned} P_p(X) &= \sum_{a^{p-1} \equiv 1 \pmod{p^2}} P_{p,a}(X) + \sum_{a^{p-1} \not\equiv 1 \pmod{p^2}} P_{p,a}(X) \\ &\leq \sum_{a^{p-1} \equiv 1 \pmod{p^2}} Q_p\left(\frac{X}{p^{p-2}}; a, p^2\right) + \sum_{a^{p-1} \not\equiv 1 \pmod{p^2}} Q_p\left(\frac{X}{p^p}; a, p^2\right) \\ &\sim \sum_{a^{p-1} \equiv 1 \pmod{p^2}} \frac{p^{p-2}}{p^p - 1} \frac{1}{\zeta(p)} \frac{X}{p^{p-2}} + \sum_{\substack{a^{p-1} \not\equiv 1 \pmod{p^2} \\ a \neq p^2}} \frac{p^{p-2}}{p^p - 1} \frac{1}{\zeta(p)} \frac{X}{p^p} \\ &\quad + \frac{p^{p-2} - 1}{p^p - 1} \frac{1}{\zeta(p)} \frac{X}{p^p} \\ &= \left((p-1) \frac{p^{p-2}}{(p^p - 1)p^{p-2}} + (p^2 - p) \frac{p^{p-2}}{(p^p - 1)p^p} + \frac{p^{p-2} - 1}{(p^p - 1)p^p} \right) \frac{X}{\zeta(p)} \\ &= \left(\frac{p^{p+1} - p^{p-1} + p^{p-2} - 1}{(p^p - 1)p^p} \right) \frac{X}{\zeta(p)}. \end{aligned}$$

Thus, we have proved that $P_p(X) \leq A_p X / \zeta(p)$.

Finally, we consider the lower bound. Since $\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt[p]{n}) \neq \mathbb{Q}(\sqrt[p]{m})$ for distinct square-

free numbers m and n , it is obvious that

$$\begin{aligned} P_p(X) &\geq \#\{n : \text{square-free} > 1, d(\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt[p]{n})) \leq X\} \\ &= \sum_{a=1}^{p^2} \#\{n : \text{square-free} > 1, n \equiv a \pmod{p^2}, d(\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt[p]{n})) \leq X\} \\ &=: \sum_{a=1}^{p^2} P'_{p,a}(X). \end{aligned}$$

If $a^{p-1} \equiv 1 \pmod{p^2}$, we have

$$P'_{p,a}(X) = \#\{n : \text{square-free} > 1, n \equiv a \pmod{p^2}, p^{p-2}n_0^{p-1} \leq X\}$$

by Lemma 2. Since $n^{p-1} \geq n_0^{p-1}$, we see

$$P'_{p,a}(X) \geq Q_2\left(\left(\frac{X}{p^{p-2}}\right)^{\frac{1}{p-1}}; a, p^2\right)$$

in this case. Similarly, if $a^{p-1} \not\equiv 1 \pmod{p^2}$, we obtain

$$P'_{p,a}(X) \geq Q_2\left(\left(\frac{X}{p^p}\right)^{\frac{1}{p-1}}; a, p^2\right)$$

by Lemma 2.

Since $\gcd(p^2, p^2) = p^2$ is not square-free, we see that

$$Q_2(X; p^2, p^2) = 0.$$

By Lemma 1, we have

$$Q_2(X; a, p^2) \sim \frac{1}{(p^2 - 1)\zeta(2)} X$$

for $a = 1, 2, \dots, p^2 - 1$.

Therefore, for a large number X , we obtain that

$$\begin{aligned} P_p(X) &\geq \sum_{a^{p-1} \equiv 1 \pmod{p^2}} Q_2\left(\left(\frac{X}{p^{p-2}}\right)^{\frac{1}{p-1}}; a, p^2\right) + \sum_{\substack{a^{p-1} \not\equiv 1 \pmod{p^2} \\ a \neq p^2}} Q_2\left(\left(\frac{X}{p^p}\right)^{\frac{1}{p-1}}; a, p^2\right) \\ &\sim (p-1) \frac{1}{(p^2 - 1)\zeta(2)} \left(\frac{X}{p^{p-2}}\right)^{\frac{1}{p-1}} + (p^2 - p) \frac{1}{(p^2 - 1)\zeta(2)} \left(\frac{X}{p^p}\right)^{\frac{1}{p-1}} \\ &= \left(\frac{1}{(p+1)p^{\frac{p-2}{p-1}}} + \frac{p}{(p+1)p^{\frac{p}{p-1}}}\right) \frac{X^{\frac{1}{p-1}}}{\zeta(2)}. \end{aligned}$$

Thus, it holds that $P_p(X) \geq B_p X^{\frac{1}{p-1}} / \zeta(2)$. This completes the proof of the assertion.

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